

CONTENT OF IMPROVEMENT OF MANAGEMENT METHODOLOGY OF MANAGEMENT SCIENCE IN INNOVATIVE EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10633551>

Abstract

The main goal of the "Management" teaching methodology in preschool education is to acquire the scientific principles and methods of management teaching as a complex system of ensuring the competitiveness of the object managed by students, and to strengthen the necessary skills for their practical implementation.

Here we will show effective methods of using interactive methods in organizing the pedagogical process by educators in preschool educational institutions. Innovative technologies in the field of education originated at the beginning of the 20th century based on the idea of humanizing the educational process. Attention is paid to satisfying the children's interests according to their wishes, respecting and loving each child, creating all the conditions for the development of his personality, and making the child's personality the center of the educational process. Paying attention to updating the content, form, tools and methods of education in recent years, searching for innovations related to preschool education, introducing it into the educational process, and the pedagogical activity of teachers, is of great importance.

In particular, the application of advanced pedagogical technologies to the pedagogical process, the introduction of innovations, the use of modern methods, and the equipping of teachers and educators with skills and qualifications are carried out as part of the tasks set before the professional development system. There is an important issue that needs to be implemented in the field of pedagogy, and that is to ensure that educators organize the pedagogical process in a purposeful, systematic and methodologically correct way based on modern methods, by being able to predict the results. Interactive methods are currently it is permissible to recognize that it is a priority aspect of educational reforms and its role in solving pedagogic problems is one of the important factors that ensure the effectiveness of education. An important aspect of the theory of pedagogical technology is determined by the ability of each pedagogue to effectively use interactive methods in the educational process in order to increase educational activity, taking into account the specific characteristics of learners of different ages.

Currently, as the psychologists of the world say, "indigo" children perceive the events happening in the world faster than adults. Therefore, today's educators face a number of urgent tasks. One of them is the use of interactive methods in the educational process. "What interactive methods can MTM educators use?" a legitimate question arises. "..We demand that the pedagogue give modern knowledge to our children. But in order to provide modern knowledge, first of all, the coach himself must have such knowledge." Teaching educators to

use interactive methods rationally, according to goals and conditions, based on didactic principles, is one of the important issues of modern pedagogy today.

Educators of kindergarden have been applying modern methods to their activities by studying scientific articles, brochures and local best practices related to preschool education. Sometimes, they use interactive methods without fully understanding their essence and purpose. Therefore, if an interactive learning environment is created in the process of professional development, and educators become its direct participants, that is, if they master each interactive method directly by themselves, adapt these methods to preschool education and put them into practice. so easy and convenient. Interactive methods such as Brainstorming, Role-playing, Working in small groups, Debate, Walk to the Gallery, Cluster, Boomerang, and Energizers can be used in preschool educational institutions. It is advisable for the teacher to use the brainstorming method at the beginning and at the end of the training to determine the children's understanding of the topic and to strengthen the knowledge they have acquired. "Working in small groups" is based on children's interaction and exchange of ideas. In this case, a given topic is developed based on analysis and verification in the group. There is something wrong with children in role-playing games the situation is given.

Children use this method to recreate real life situations. In the debate method, children are given a topic the day before. Children find answers to questions by asking their parents, and the answers to the given questions are conducted on the basis of "discussion". Today, although there are clear concepts and ideas about pedagogical technology, pedagogues of preschool educational institutions have problems such as not being able to distinguish technology from methodology. However, there are significant differences between them, and theoretical information about them is given below. Pedagogical technology is a process that guarantees teaching a child to be independent, to learn, to think. The methodology depends on the knowledge, skills, abilities, personal qualities and temperament of the pedagogue and is a set of teaching methods and ways convenient for a certain person, pedagogue.

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